

Reaction of Diazonium Salts with Hydroxymethylen *cyclo*Hexanones and Cyclic β -Diketones.

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It was observed by one of us (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1915, 107, 1847) that in a conjugated double bonded system of the type $O=C-\overset{|}{C}=\overset{|}{C}-R$, the ethylenic linking is more reactive than the carbonyl group. Thus, the action of cyanacetamide on hydroxymethylene *cyclo*hexanones was shown to proceed in the following way giving rise to quinoline derivatives:—

Burdhan suggested, however, (Thesis for the D.Sc. degree, Calcutta University, 1924) that the reaction above might also be explained as well by assuming the presence of a keto-aldehyde phase in hydroxymethylene *cyclo*hexanone in which the aldehyde group is naturally expected to be more reactive than the keto, thus leading to the formation of a quinoline derivative and not an *iso*quinoline one as would be the case if the keto group were more reactive. But this view of Burdhan's is rendered improbable by a recent work of Sen and Bose (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 51) who found that the reactivity of a β -diketone with cyanacetamide tends to disappear where the chance of enolisation is least possible.

As in hydroxymethylene *cyclo*hexanone the enolisation is at the formyl group, and since quinoline derivatives are actually obtained by condensing them with cyanacetamide, it is not necessary to accept Burdhan's view to explain this course of reaction. The ordinary assumption that hydroxymethylene ketones are permanently enolised β -diketones, if true for open-chain compounds, is, however,

not true for cyclic hydroxymethylene ketones. The existence of a considerable proportion of a keto-aldehyde phase along with the keto-enol in the latter, is proved in the present work. The bromine titration method (an account of which will be very shortly communicated) also points to the same conclusion. When methyl iodide is allowed to react with the sodium salt of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* in absolute alcoholic solution, (i) O-methyl ether of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone*, and (ii) *ortho*-methyl *cyclohexanone* are obtained. Obviously, the chance of enolisation under the experimental condition is great, and as such the exclusive formation of the O-methyl ether should be expected. In reality, however, about 40 per cent. of the reaction product is *ortho*-methyl *cyclohexanone*. The presence, therefore, of a considerable proportion of the keto-aldehyde phase even in absolute alcoholic solution, must account for the formation of *orthomethylcyclohexanone*, unless indeed one assumes the wandering of the methyl group from oxygen to carbon.

If, however, the sodium salt of hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* is prepared by the addition of metallic sodium to the hydroxymethylene ketone in benzene suspension, the product obtained on methylation (also in benzene solution) gives on treatment with cold potash, *orthomethylcyclohexanone* as the main product which establishes the presence of a keto-aldehyde phase.

The presence of the keto-aldehyde in hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* is further evident from the following reaction which was next studied *in extenso*. When diazonium chloride reacts with hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* in presence of sodium acetate, the reaction product, obtained in nearly quantitative yield, is in a state of fairly good purity, and corresponds to a monophenylhydrazone of diketohexamethylene. Unfortunately, after the work had proceeded far we noticed that Coffey (*Abs. Chem. Soc., Lond.* 1928, (i), 808; *Rec. trav. Chim.*, 1928, 42, 528) had already studied this particular case in this type of reaction, *i.e.*, the action of diazonium chloride on hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone*. No doubt this took away much of the real interest of the subject, but on extending the reaction to acetyl and carboethoxy *cycloketones*, important differentiating properties of β -diketones and hydroxymethylene *cycloketones* were observed.

The action of diazonium chloride on hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* gives, as already stated, a monophenylhydrazone of diketocyclohexane (*cf.* Coffey); we have found that with the various hydroxymethylene *cycloketones* and diazo salts, the monophenylhydrazones are invariably obtained. That they are monophenylhydrazones is established from the following two facts:—

(i) When they are heated for sometime with glacial acetic acid, a conversion analogous to Fischer's indole synthesis takes place, giving rise to carbazole derivatives.

(ii) On heating the original reaction products with phenylhydrazine, osazones are readily obtained. Thus mono-phenylhydrazone of diketohexamethylene yields the same osazone as was prepared by Kötze from oxycyclohexanone (*Abs.* 1913, i, 1201).

As is obvious, the formation of monophenylhydrazone from hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* and diazonium salts, necessitates the removal of the formyl group to give the necessary hydrogen for the formation of phenylhydrazone.

The reaction can be expressed as below :—

Very recently Benary, Meyer and Charisius have shown (*Ber.*, 1926, 59, 109) that open-chain hydroxymethylene ketones react with diazobenzene chloride giving the following type of compounds:—

In these cases the formyl group is intact. That the formyl group is split off from hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanones* under similar conditions is confirmed by analysis and the facts that (i) a distinct odour of ethyl formate is obtained as the reaction proceeds and that (ii) the filtrate from the reaction product gives a distillate which reduces mercuric chloride to mercurous chloride. The elimination of the formyl group, so peculiar in the case of cyclic hydroxymethylene ketones, can be explained thus: In open-chain hydroxymethy-

lene compounds there is hydrogen available for the formation of phenylhydrazone, whilst in cyclic hydroxymethylene ketones no such hydrogen is present, and as such if the tendency is to produce a hydrazone under the experimental conditions, the formyl group, by splitting off, supplies the hydrogen.* That they are hydrazones has been conclusively proved alike by our own work as also by previous workers (V. Meyer, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 11; Japp and Klingemann, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1888, 53, 519; Pechmann, *Ber.*, 1892, 25, 8190; *Ber.*, 1894, 27, 219; Favrel, *Compt. rend.*, 1901, 132, 41; *Compt. rend.*, 1892, 134, 1812; Rabischogon, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1904, (iii) 31, 76; Dimroth, *Ber.*, 1908, 41, 4012, etc.). The tendency to form phenylhydrazones in such cases is so great that CO₂ and acetyl group are split off respectively from alkylacetoacetic acids and alkylacetoacetic esters (*cf.* Japp and Klingemann, *loc. cit.*).

Mention has already been made that the course of reaction of diazonium chlorides with hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanones* is different from that with other cyclic β -diketones, such as acetyl *cyclohexanones*. If this were not so, the same hydrazone would be obtained whether one started with hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone* or acetyl *cyclohexanone* (or *cyclohexanone* carboxylate). The reaction probably proceeds, however, in the following way:—

* The question may arise, why is the resulting compound a hydrazone and not an azo-derivative?

This point is at present under investigation and is expected to be elucidated by preparing the acetylphenylhydrazone of diketohexamethylene.

The explanation of the non-elimination of the acyl group here, as distinct from the formyl group in hydroxymethylene *cyclohexanone*, probably lies in the fact that the asymmetrical formyl-phenylhydrazone is unknown doubtless on account of its instability, whereas acetyl-phenylhydrazone and carbethoxy-phenylhydrazone are stable. No carbazole derivatives have been obtained from these even on prolonged boiling with acetic acid, probably because of the difficulty of obtaining the hydrogen necessary for the elimination of ammonia. A further peculiarity of these acyl phenylhydrazones is their solubility in dilute alkali and precipitation on acidification without any decomposition. The behaviour is difficult to explain unless one assumes that the ketonic group left free enolises. Sodium carbonate solution does not dissolve them. In the case of the monophenylhydrazone of diketocyclohexanes formed by the action of diazo salts with hydroxymethylene-*cyclohexanones* this solubility in alkali is extremely small although a little does dissolve. Probably the absence of any strongly acidic group in the compound accounts for this depressed solubility. The question, however, has to be left open for the present.

A fact of considerable interest has been noticed in one or two cases of these condensation products which points to the existence of isomers (*cf. J. pr. Chem.*, 1892, (ii) 46, 579; 1893, 47, 591, *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 1965). Thus the monotoyl hydrazone of 1-methyl-2 : 3 diketocyclohexane exists in two forms, one melting at 91-93°, and the other at 117-118°. The possibility of the existence of isomers is seen from the following representation :—

In other instances, although isomers of distinctly different melting points have not been isolated, their indifferent melting points would lead one to suspect the existence of these as mixtures.

EXPERIMENTAL.

1-Hydroxymethylene-cyclohexane-2-one and Diazobenzene Chloride: Formation of cyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-phenyl hydrazone.

1-Hydroxymethylene-cyclohexane-2-one was obtained by the usual method of Borsche (A., 1910, i, 890).

In a beaker of about 600 c.c. capacity, 1-hydroxymethylene-cyclohexane-2-one (10 g.) was mixed with a saturated solution of sodium acetate (25 g.). The turbid solution was made clear by the addition of a sufficient quantity of alcohol and allowed to cool in a bath of freezing mixture. After it had cooled to 0°, a diazo-solution obtained from one molecular equivalent of freshly distilled aniline (78 g.) was added to it in small quantities with vigorous stirring. The operation was completed in the course of about half an hour when a yellow precipitate was obtained. A distinct odour of ethyl formate was noticed as the reaction proceeded. The yellow precipitate was then rapidly filtered and the filtrate was preserved for further treatment as will be described below. The precipitate was thoroughly washed with water to free it from sodium acetate and other adhering impurities. This was then dried and weighed, a nearly theoretical yield being obtained. It was found convenient to crystallise it from hot glacial acetic acid in which it is moderately soluble. It was found also expedient to boil up with animal charcoal before crystallisation as otherwise the colour of the crystals appeared to be somewhat dirty. The crystals were beautiful, lustrous and reddish-yellow in colour and melted at 181°-185°. (Found: N, 14.10; C, 70.99; H, 7.13. $C_{12}H_{14}ON_2$ requires N, 13.86; C, 71.28; H, 6.93 per cent.)

This was moderately soluble in most of the organic solvents. It also slightly dissolves in dilute alkali.

Confirmation of the Presence of Ethyl Formate in the Reaction Mixture.

The filtrate mentioned above was distilled on a water-bath and the distillate was collected between 53° and 80°. In the distillate, a strong odour of ethyl formate was noticed. On addition of a solution of mercuric chloride to a little of it at first a white turbidity was formed which on standing settled down to a white precipitate

due to the formation of mercurous chloride. The smallness of the precipitate was perhaps due to the presence of only a small quantity of ethyl formate.

1-Keto-tetrahydro-carbazole.

A few grams of the monophenylhydrazone obtained were dissolved in an excess of glacial acetic acid and heated under reflux for one hour. When cold the solution was diluted with water when a brownish white precipitate was obtained. This was filtered and recrystallised from hot 50 per cent acetic acid. Greyish white needles melting at 168° were obtained. (Found: N, 7.78. $C_{12}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.5 per cent.).

cycloHexane-1:2-dione-diphenylhydrazones.

The monophenylhydrazone obtained, an equivalent quantity of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, and sodium acetate in excess were heated on a water-bath for one hour in alcoholic solution under reflux. Sodium chloride separated, which dissolved on the addition of water, and a yellow precipitate was obtained. This was thoroughly washed and recrystallised from hot alcohol by the addition of a few drops of water. Fine yellow coloured crystals, m.p. 153°-154°. (Found: N, 19.36; C, 78.87; H, 7.08. $C_{18}H_{16}N_4$ requires N, 19.18; C, 78.98; H, 6.84 per cent.).

This compound was found to be identical with that obtained by Kötze (cf. A., 1913, i, 1201) by the action of phenylhydrazine on 2-hydroxycyclohexane-1-one prepared by the hydrolysis of chlor-2-cyclohexanone-1. A mixture of Kötze's compound and ours showed no lowering of melting point. While preparing Kötze's compound it was found that the same could be prepared much easier in the following way. Instead of hydrolysing chlor-2-cyclohexanone-1 by K_2CO_3 and then treating the 2-hydroxycyclohexanone-1 thus isolated with phenylhydrazine, the osazone could be obtained by hydrolysing 2-chloro-cyclohexanone with KOH solution and treating it with phenylhydrazine after acidification.

1-Hydroxymethylene-cyclohexane-2-one and p-Diazotoluene Chloride: Formation of cycloHexane-1:2-dione-mono-p-tolylhydrazones.

The condensation product was obtained as previously using p-toluidine for diazotisation, the yield being 97%. After recrystalli-

sation from hot glacial acetic acid and also boiling with animal charcoal, it was obtained as yellow crystals melting at 190° (Found: N, 18.80; C, 72.51; H, 7.60. $C_{11}H_{11}ON_2$ requires N, 12.96; C, 72.22; H, 7.41 per cent.)

1-Keto-tetrahydro-3-methyl-carbazole.

This was obtained as before by heating in an excess of glacial acetic acid the monotoyl-hydrazone obtained as above for one hour. After recrystallisation by boiling with animal charcoal from 50 per cent acetic acid, it was obtained as colourless flakes sintering at 192° and melting at 194° (Found: N, 7.29. $C_{11}H_{11}ON$ requires N, 7.03 per cent.).

cycloHexane-dione-1-phenyl-2-p-tolyhydrazone.

It was obtained as previously by the action of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and excess of sodium acetate on cyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-p-tolyhydrazone. When recrystallised from alcohol diluted with a few drops of water it was obtained as yellow coloured crystals sintering at 145° and melting at 150° . The melting point was not very sharp even after two or three crystallisations. (Found: N, 18.72; C, 74.08; H, 7.60. $C_{11}H_{12}N_2$ requires N, 18.29; C, 74.50; H, 7.18 per cent.).

1-Hydroxymethylene-cyclohexane-2-one and Diazo-p-nitrobenzene Chloride: Formation of cycloHexane-1:2-dionemono-p-nitrophenyl hydrazone.

The condensation was effected as previously using diazotised p-nitraniline. The product was crystallised from hot glacial acetic acid in which it is sparingly soluble. The crystals were obtained as dark brown needles, melting between 228° and 230° blackening a few degrees earlier (223°). The yield in this case was nearly 93 per cent. (Found: N, 17.32. $C_{11}H_{11}O_2N_2$ requires N, 17.00 per cent.).

It is insoluble in most of the organic solvents except in glacial acetic acid in which it is sparingly soluble. It also slightly dissolves in dilute alkali.

1-Keto-tetrahydro-3-nitro-carbazole.

This was obtained as previously by boiling the phenylhydrazone obtained as above with an excess of glacial acetic acid for two hours

and a half. This was recrystallised from hot alcohol. Light brown crystals sinter at 209° and melt at 212°. (Found: N, 12·35. C₁₈H₁₀O₂N₂ requires N, 12·17 per cent.).

cycloHexane-dione 1-p-nitrophenyl-2-phenylhydrazones.

Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride dissolved in alcohol was mixed with a saturated solution of sodium acetate and to this was added the phenylhydrazone obtained as above which remained in suspension owing to its insolubility in alcohol. This was heated on the water-bath under reflux for 2 hours when the colour of the suspended phenylhydrazone was found to have changed from reddish-brown to scarlet-red. This was filtered, washed with water, and crystallised from hot alcohol in which it was sparingly soluble. It was obtained as scarlet coloured crystalline powder having m.p. 215°—217°. It is insoluble in most other organic solvents. (Found: N, 20·53. C₁₈H₁₁N₂O₂ requires N, 20·77 per cent.).

1-Hydroxymethylene-3-methyl-cyclohexane 2-one and Diazobenzene Chloride: Formation of 3-methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione-monophenylhydrazone.

1-Hydroxymethylene-3-methylcyclohexane-2-one was obtained in the usual way by condensing together *o*-methyl-cyclohexanone and isoamyl formate. The liquid boils at 112°—114°/40 mm.

The condensation was effected in the usual way between 1-hydroxymethylene-3-methylcyclohexane-2-one and diazobenzene chloride. The yield in this case was somewhat less (about 85 per cent.). As this was found to be a low melting substance it was crystallised in the following way:—It was first dissolved in alcohol, boiled with animal charcoal and filtered. Then the solution was cooled and drops of water added till turbid. On keeping the solution at that condition for some time beautiful yellow crystals appeared which melted with following characteristics. It began to sinter at 83°, then partly melted at 91°, got turbid, and the turbidity cleared at 131°. Even after crystallisation for three times no improvement was noticed in its m.p. Its analyses for nitrogen,

carbon and hydrogen point, however, to its homogeneous composition. It seems therefore, to be a mixture of two isomers as already mentioned (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 18.08; C, 71.90; H, 7.68. $C_{11}H_{10}ON$, requires N, 12.96; C, 72.21; H, 7.46 per cent.)

It is extremely soluble in most of the organic solvents. It also slightly dissolves in dilute alkali. It is very unstable. The well-shaped crystals when kept in a sample tube gets resinified within a fortnight.

1-Keto-2-methyl-tetrahydro-carbazole.

This was obtained as usual by heating the monophenylhydrazone in an excess of glacial acetic acid for about ten minutes. If it is boiled for a longer time it gets charred. On cooling it was diluted with water when a brownish black precipitate was obtained. This gave colourless crystals, m.p. $171^{\circ}-73^{\circ}$ after boiling with animal charcoal in alcohol. It can also be crystallised from 50 per cent. acetic acid. (Found: N, 7.06; C, 78.08; H, 6.81. $C_{11}H_{11}NO$ requires N, 7.08; C, 78.38; H, 6.53 per cent.)

3-Methylcyclohexane-1:2-dione-diphenylhydrazone.

This was obtained as usual by heating phenylhydrazine hydrochloride, excess of sodium acetate and monophenylhydrazone prepared as above, in an alcoholic solution for half an hour. This was filtered and recrystallised from alcohol by adding a few drops of water. Fine yellow crystals, m. p. $151^{\circ}-153^{\circ}$. (Found: N, 18.55; C, 74.89; H, 7.26. $C_{19}H_{17}N_4$ requires N, 18.3; C, 74.50; H, 7.19 per cent.)

1-Hydroxymethylene-3-methyl-cyclohexane-2-one and p-Diazotoluene Chloride: Formation of 3-methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-p-tolylhydrazone.

The condensation was effected in the usual way, the yield being about 85 per cent. It was crystallised in the same way as in the case of monophenyl-hydrazone. But while crystallising, two products having different melting points were isolated. At first the crude product was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal. This was filtered and to the cold solution drops of water were added till the solution was turbid. On standing crystals separated. This was filtered and the filtrate preserved. The crystals so obtained were recrystallised again and again for 3 or 4 times from dilute alcohol. From this, yellow needle-shaped crystals m.p. 117° .

180° were obtained. On the addition of more water to the mother-liquor after first filtration, a product was obtained which on recrystallisation from alcohol diluted with water melted at 91°—93°. On analysis the two were found to have identical composition and hence they seemed to be isomers. [Found: (i) m.p. 91°—93°, N, 12·47; C, 72·61; H, 8·30; (ii) m.p. 117°—118°, C, 72·69; H, 8·32. $C_{14}H_{18}ON_4$ requires N, 12·17; C, 73·04; H, 7·83 per cent.).

This is also very soluble in most organic solvents. It slightly dissolves in dilute alkali. This is also unstable, as after keeping it for more than one month in a sample tube, tarry matters separated.

1-Keto-2-methyl-tetrahydro-3-methylcarbazole,

This was obtained as before by boiling the tolylhydrazone in an excess of glacial acetic acid for ten minutes. Longer heating chars the product. When cold, it was precipitated with water and the product was recrystallised from 50 per cent. acetic acid after boiling with animal charcoal. Colourless crystals, m.p. 195°. It can also be crystallised from 50 per cent. alcohol. (Found: N, 6·88; C, 78·89; H, 7·22. $C_{14}H_{18}ON$ requires N, 6·57; C, 77·87; H, 7·04 per cent.).

3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione-1-tolylhydrazone-2-phenylhydrazone,

This was obtained as previously by heating the alcoholic solution of the tolylhydrazone prepared, phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and sodium acetate on a water-bath for about half an hour. The product obtained when crystallised from hot alcohol came down in beautiful yellow crystals, m.p. 158°-159°. (Found: N, 17·63. $C_{20}H_{24}N_4$ requires N, 17·50 per cent.).

1-Hydroxymethylene-3-methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione and β -Diazonaphthalene Chloride: Formation of 3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione-naphthylhydrazone.

The condensation of the two was effected in the same way as before, using diazotised β -naphthylamine (yield about 55% of the theoretical).

The condensation product so obtained contained much tarry matters; so it was at first dried in a vacuum desiccator and then treated with petroleum ether in which the tarry matters dissolved. Then the product was crystallised from cold methyl alcoholic solution diluted with a few drops of water. The crystals obtained were

reddish yellow in colour and melted between 85° and 88°. It is fairly soluble in most organic solvents and slightly in dilute alkali. It is also unstable, tarry matters being separated from well-defined crystals after sometime. (Found: N, 10.90. C₁₁H₉ON₂ requires N, 10.53 per cent.).

1-Keto-2-methyl-tetrahydro-naphtho-carbasole.

This was obtained as previously by heating the naphthyl-hydrazone in an excess of glacial acetic acid for ten minutes. The product obtained was crystallised from 50 per cent. acetic acid when greyish white crystals were formed melting at 225° blackening at 212°. (Found: N, 5.39. C₁₁H₉ON requires N, 5.62 per cent.).

The osazone has not been obtained by the further action of phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in presence of sodium acetate.

1-Acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one and Diazobenzene Chloride: Formation of cyclohexane-1: 2-dione-mono-acetylphenylhydrazones.

1-Acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one was prepared according to Lesser's method (*Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1900, (iii) 23, 370.)

1-Acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one (3 g.) dissolved in a little alcohol was mixed with a saturated solution of sodium acetate (15 g. in 25 c.c. of water) and the turbidity that ensued was just dissolved by the addition of a further quantity of alcohol. The solution was then allowed to cool in a freezing bath. A diazobenzenechloride solution was prepared from an equivalent quantity of freshly distilled aniline. The diazo solution was then poured into the ice-cooled acetylcyclohexanone solution adding a small portion at a time and stirring well the mixtures with a glass rod. Contrary to previous experience, instead of a crystalline precipitate the mixture turned into an emulsion from which an oil separated at the end of the reaction. The reaction mixture was found to solidify on keeping in the freezing bath for 2-3 hours and then at the room temperature overnight. The solid mass was next morning filtered and washed with a little rectified spirit which dissolved the tarry matters. The yield was nearly 60%. It could be obtained pure from hot 50% acetic acid after three crystallisations, but it was found convenient to purify it as follows:—It was reprecipitated by acidification with acetic acid from its solution in dilute alkali in which it was found to dissolve (*loc. cit*). The reprecipitated substance was then dissolved in 50% acetic acid and boiled with animal charcoal. The filtered solution,

on cooling, deposited crystals which were again crystallised from acetic acid. The substance was obtained as fine yellow plates, m.p. 159°-161°. (Found: N, 11.60. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 11.48 per cent.).

It dissolves in acetic acid, ethyl alcohol, methyl alcohol etc., but is insoluble in benzene, petroleum ether and chloroform. It dissolves completely in dilute alkali from which it can be recovered unchanged by acidification.

1-Acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one and p-Diazotoluene Chloride: Formation of cyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-acetyl-tolylhydrazone.

The condensation was effected in the same way as above using *p*-toluidine. In this case also an oil separated which on keeping overnight solidified (yield 60% of the theoretical). This was crystallised in the same way as above by first dissolving in dilute alkali and the product after acidification was thrice crystallised from 50% acetic acid when beautiful yellow plates were obtained melting at 151°-153°. (Found: N, 10.95. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent.).

It also dissolves in dilute alkali from which it can be obtained unchanged by acidification. It is fairly soluble in most organic solvents.

3-Methyl-1-acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one and Diazobenzene Chloride: Formation of 3-Methylcyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-acetylphenylhydrazone.

3-Methyl-1-acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one was prepared according to Lesser's method. From 50 gms. of *o*-methyl-cyclohexanone only 9 g. of 3-methyl-1-acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one were obtained. The liquid boils at 100°-105°/15 mm.

The condensation was effected in the same way as above. The yield was the same as in the former case. An oil separated which on keeping overnight solidified. It is best crystallised by thrice dissolving in 50% acetic acid. The method of dissolving in dilute alkali and reprecipitating with acetic acid was not suitable. Yellow plates, m.p. 137°-140°, were obtained. (Found: N, 10.90. $C_{11}H_{16}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10.85 per cent.).

This also dissolves in dilute alkali and can be obtained unchanged by acidification. It is soluble in most organic media but is insoluble in petroleum ether.

*3-Methyl-1-acetyl-cyclohexane-2-one and p-Diazotoluene Chloride :
Formation of 3-Methyl-cyclohexane-1:2-dione-mono-acetyltolylhydra-
zone.*

The condensation product was obtained as previously as an oil at first which, on keeping over-night, solidified. The yield was the same as before. This is best crystallised from hot benzene, when it is obtained as light yellow crystals, m.p. 117°-120°. (Found: N, 10·15. $C_{18}H_{26}O$ N requires N, 10·28 per cent.).

It also dissolves in dilute alkali from which it can be precipitated unchanged by acid. It is soluble in most of the organic solvents.

*1-Carbethoxy-cyclohexane-2-one and Diazobenzene Chloride :
Formation of cycloHexane-1:2-dione-mono-carbethoxy-phenylhydra-
zone.*

1-Carbethoxy-cyclohexane-2-one was prepared according to the method of Kötze, (A., 1905, 346). The condensation was effected as usual by adding the diazo-solution to ethylcyclohexanonecarboxylate in a saturated solution of sodium acetate. At the end of the reaction an oil separated, which on keeping overnight solidified. This is best crystallised by first dissolving in dilute alkali and then precipitating by acidification. After two crystallisations from 50% acetic acid (using animal charcoal) long needle-shaped light yellow crystals were obtained, m.p. 90°-92°. (Found: N, 10·11. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_2$ requires N, 10·22 per cent.). It is moderately soluble in most of the organic solvents.

*1-Carbethoxy-cyclohexane-2-one and p-Diazotoluene Chloride :
Formation of cycloHexane-1:2 dione-mono-carbethoxytolylhydrazone.*

The condensation was effected as usual. The product was an oil which afterwards solidified. It was found convenient to crystallise it from methyl alcohol diluted with a few drops of water. The substance was obtained as brown crystals, m.p. 97°-99°. (Found: N, 9·86. $C_{18}H_{20}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9·72 per cent.).

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